

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report of project policy briefs which distill the key project findings to be presented at policy events.

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WP10

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Executive summary

As part of nextGEMS' mission to bring together cutting-edge climate modelling and policymakers, the project developed policy briefs and conducted policy briefings. These briefs serve as tools to stimulate reflection and dialogue with stakeholders by focusing on the following aspects: usability of kilometre-scale Earth system models, the creation of collaborative research environments, and the application of advanced climate science to address pressing issues like food security in Africa. Aligned with the project's goals of science communication and co-produced knowledge, the policy briefs aimed to translate complex scientific concepts into accessible, yet accurate, formats appropriate for policymakers. They are an affective entry points for engaging policy audiences.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	no

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	no
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	no
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	yes

Synergies

This report about policy brief has strong linkages with all the WPs of nextGEMS. The report presents the work conducted to produce three policy briefs:

- on 'Building User Communities around Next Generation Earth System Models'
- on 'Food Security in West Africa'.
- on 'Reaching the last mile with km-scale Earth System Models'

The synergies between this deliverable and other work packages (WPs) within the project are manifold. The first policy brief is closely aligned with the activities carried out under WP10, as it addresses the co-production approach that underpinned the hackathons and highlights their role in fostering community-building among researchers and stakeholders. The second brief is strongly linked to both WP6 and WP10. It connects to WP6 through its focus on simulations related to fisheries, and to WP10 through the participatory processes and engagement efforts involved in the co-production of the storyline. Lastly, the third policy brief reflects the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS project and is therefore relevant to all WPs. It articulates the scientific ambitions of the initiative and their broader implications for the advancement of climate science.

1 Policy briefs and policy briefing: informing policy-making

Policy briefs and briefings have become a key tool in science dissemination efforts for a very specific target audience: policy-makers. Policy briefs synthesize the main lessons learned around key themes of research endeavors, to enable fast dissemination and potential uptake of the recommendations contained within. Policy briefing joins these efforts to have direct contact with policy-makers through meetings and events in which the outcomes of the projects are explained tailored to the main interests of the audience.

In nextGEMS, policy briefs and briefings contribute to the general communication concept addressed to the general public and media, to add a key recipient of its scientific results which are policy makers at European and international levels, such as the European Commission, as well as other international bodies such as the United Nations.

The following policy briefs and briefings have been delivered:

1. on 'Building User Communities around Next Generation Earth System Models', summarizing our experiences in working to integrate User communities into the development of storm-resolving Earth System Models. This policy brief was intended to inform the European strategy for Earth-system modeling, particularly as a component of 'Destination Earth', and thus targets the European Commission and relevant Directorates-General.
2. on 'Food Security in West Africa'. This policy briefing actively engaged policy-makers from the affected region (ACMAD, AGRHYMET, ECREEE, ECOWAS, African Climate Policy Center). The briefing consisted of presenting the findings about the maritime productivity and its effects on fishery and the latest findings from investigating West African Monsoons and rainfall distribution and extremes in Sahel. This question has been receiving increasing interest and triggering scientific and policy debates.

Additionally, NextGEMS prepared a third policy brief summarizing the broader recommendations for SR-ESM:

3. on 'Reaching the last mile with km-scale Earth System Models'. This policy brief targets EU policymakers, aiming to raise awareness of the opportunities and challenges associated with km-scale modeling. It presents these models as powerful tools for improving climate projections, particularly regarding extreme weather events, and for informing adaptation and disaster risk management policies.

The nextGEMS policy briefs and briefings complement project scientific outcomes that have become available through the effective communication activities. The aim of these efforts is to robustly contribute to the assessment activities organized by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), and similar regional activities such as those of the German Excellence Cluster, Climate, Climate Change and Society (CLICCS) and their yearly assessments, called Hamburg Climate Future Outlooks.

2 Methodology

2.1 Co-design

Policy briefs

The policy briefs were developed by members of the nextGEMS consortium, primarily scientists and communication experts, with feedback loops internal to the project community. While no external co-design mechanisms were employed, the process sought to reflect both scientific insights and practical considerations for policy and research actors.

For the visual design of the policy briefs, we opted for the use of canva with the colour palette associated to the nextGEMS communication material. The final outcome of the design is annexed to this document.

Policy briefing

The policy briefings actively presented the outcomes of nextGEMS to a targeted audience. They situated their relevance within the needs and challenges of policy-makers during several events attended by the main regional authorities.

2.2 Dissemination

Dissemination was conducted through targeted policy-oriented events and networks, with the aim of amplifying the visibility of nextGEMS insights and engaging with relevant stakeholders across EU, and West African institutions and research communities.

3 Results

3.1 PB1: Building User Communities around Next Generation Earth System Models

The first policy brief focuses on how to design projects in the climate community, including those that consider hackathons as spaces for collaborative model development and community-building. It targets the EU research and innovation community, including those who design, fund, and participate in collaborative research projects.

The brief builds on empirical evidence from the series of hackathons held within the nextGEMS project, showcasing how these events:

- Enable peer learning and interdisciplinary exchange.
- Support the emergence of new scientific collaborations and networks.
- Offer a co-production format that fosters trust, creativity, and shared ownership of technical

and scientific outcomes.

The brief offers recommendations for integrating such collaborative structures into research project design—highlighting how intentional structuring of events can contribute to long-term community development and improve the societal relevance of scientific outputs.

3.2 PB2: Food Security in West Africa

For the policy briefing around the topic 'Food Security in West Africa', there were several events in which nextGEMS scientists presented the scientific outcomes of the project. This included the Blue Belt initiative, in the context of the "African Ocean Week". These events had the presence of 32 ministerial delegations, in addition to representatives of the African Union (AU), and the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) and Directorate Generals (DGs) from the EC.

These are the main events:

- 3rd High Level Conference of the Blue Belt Initiative (BBI) "Building a foundation to boost Blue Food and Jobs under a Blue Economy development approach"; 7-8 October 2024; BBI, <http://bluebeltinitiative.com/notre-plateforme/nos-partenaires/>. During this event, the "Déclaration de Tanger" was presented. The themes from nextGEMS presented in this event were the impact of climate change on fisheries in North West Africa and how to foster international collaboration with Africa, starting with the IPCC and including initiatives such as nextGEMS. Moreover, a session about "Science and data" was also conducted by a nextGEMS scientist and presented at the ministerial segment of the conference..
- African Consultation in Preparation for the 3rd United Nations Ocean Conference (UNOC-3); 9 October 2024, organised by the Moroccan Ministry of Fisheries, Environment and and the UN. nextGEMS was part of the Advisory Scientific COmmittee (n=4). The event brought together 30 African states, ministers, scientists, and diverse stakeholders to share their perspectives, priorities, and recommendations for sustainable ocean governance. The key messages included better knowledge on Climate Change impact.
- On the sidelines: 1st Special Session of the Conference of Ministers of the Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission (SRFC), with presence of 7 member states. In this policy event, the signature of the SCS convention was achieved, the culmination of 7 years of negotiations, an aspect of key interest to the European Union.
- Blue Africa Summit, 10 October; established an initial roadmap for the major challenges faced in marine Africa.

3.3 PB3: Reaching the last mile with km-scale Earth System Models

This policy brief draws on internal expertise within the nextGEMS community and reflects shared concerns about making next-generation climate science actionable, equitable, and inclusive. Key messages include:

- Enhanced climate information: Km-scale models provide finer spatial resolution and improved understanding of atmospheric processes, offering better-informed projections at regional scales.
- Science-policy usability gap: Despite the increasing availability of high-quality climate data, it is not yet translating into widespread, evidence-based policy action.
- System-level recommendations: A set of policy options is proposed to ensure the science reaches its intended users, including:
 - Supporting trans-disciplinary collaboration between climate scientists and user-oriented experts.
 - Addressing data access barriers and improving usability for non-technical users.
 - Retaining early-career talent by recognizing the technical work underpinning scientific advancement.
 - Encouraging public-private partnerships to support the infrastructure needed for this modeling frontier.

4 Conclusion

As part of nextGEMS' commitment to bridging advanced climate modeling and societal needs, policy briefs and briefings have been developed to support reflection and dialogue with key actors. These briefs address both the usability of km-scale Earth system models and the design of collaborative research environments, as well as how this advanced science can support aspects of key concern such as food security in Africa. These policy briefs align with the project's goals of science dissemination and knowledge co-production. Overall, policy briefs allow:

- Translating complex science into accessible formats without oversimplification.
- Creating low-threshold entry points for engagement with policy audiences.
- Recognizing hackathons as valuable venues for participatory knowledge production, particularly when repeated over time and integrated into broader project strategies.

Appendices

DECEMBER 2024

POLICY BRIEF

REACHING THE LAST MILE WITH KM-SCALE EARTH SYSTEM MODELS

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CONTEXT

km-scale Earth-system models

New vanguard services, products and cooperation hubs are created around km-scale earth system models. Examples are the European Union's Flagship Initiative Destination Earth (DestinE) or the recent Earth Visualisation Engines (EVE) ambition, both **pursuing essential societal goals** such as to "support future evidence-based policy-making" or "empower people to respond to the immense and urgent challenge of climate change" accordingly. However, these initiatives need targeted efforts to ensure that their outputs - of **quality and relevance**, but also costly - do not face the usability gap. Namely, despite the increases in climate data quality, evidence-based decision-making for climate action has not followed suit (1, 2, 3).

In this policy brief, we analyse the topic, to subsequently consider policy options which could support this leading-edge science to be of real and effective service to society.

BETTER FOR WHAT

Due to their ability to capture fine-scale atmospheric processes such as convective storms, local wind patterns, and precipitation more effectively, **km-scale earth system models are expected to provide better future climate information data** at different time scales, whilst also providing better understanding of extreme events (4). More precision with regards to extreme events can aid in disaster preparedness and risk mitigation efforts. These models may also offer **better long-term climate projections** by representing regional climate variations, feedback mechanisms, and interactions between different components of the Earth system (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land surface) (5, 6).

Finally, km-scale earth system models are expected to allow for an increased understanding of regional climate variability, which is crucial for **assessing the impacts of climate change on specific locations and sectors** such as agriculture, water resources, and human health (7). Assimilation of diverse observational data sets, including satellite data, ground-based measurements, and remote sensing data, can lead to improved model validation, calibration, and data assimilation techniques, reducing also uncertainty in km-scale model outputs, which is one of the concerns of more sceptical perspectives on their relevance. The opportunity of these models to be used as a **powerful visualisation device** is not to be understated, as it can bring climate change closer to non-technical users.

BETTER FOR WHOM (I)

Science

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For science and scientists themselves, km-scale modelling can bring new breakthroughs and due to the required infrastructure, it can give important technological skills to those scientists involved in developing it. However, these pioneers and, above all, early career researchers, carry the pressure from the friction between data science and climate science. The required data-intensive activities mean that the day-to-day of these scientists is spent fixing bugs and improving code (sometimes rewarding, but not always acknowledged), which can be demotivating tasks if the end-goal of improving climate science gets lost in translation and leave them prone to leave science provided that these skills are highly valued in the private sector (8). Additionally, engaging communities such as technology and science enthusiasts or other stakeholders with advanced technical skills at early stages of infrastructure development is crucial: they are the key group to see how well integration works with impact models as the linkage towards evidence-based policy-making in a myriad of sectors.

Furthermore, the development of km-scale modelling is expensive and can lead to the technological lock-in (9). What are the opportunity costs? How to allocate funding and computing resources in order to allow these advancements? Solutions go through alliances with machine learning (ML) researchers, who have become a part of the endeavour, as well as inter-institutional collaborations between research centres. And a clear responsibility distribution, should allow other initiatives – e.g. CMIP and CORDEX – to maintain their activities in spite of the resources required to push km-scale climate modelling forward.

BETTER FOR WHOM (II)

Policy

For governments, these models can be of service to multiple governance levels for impacts, adaptation, and risk management strategies but a key point is the unequal access to information and resource capacities (10). Although the latest models are not yet ready to be used, continuous engagement work with such users should ensure that the outputs of these efforts are adequate and fit for purpose. Finally, the society involves communities, companies (small-and-medium and large enterprises) and societal representatives. For small companies, access to this data can mean that their services can be made more resilient. For big companies, the integration into their business models and the offering of paid services (11). Finally, if this new infrastructure proves accessible and usable, it could accommodate access to high quality climate information to society at large.

Society

Figure, ref. 12

THE WAY FORWARD

THE FOLLOWING SET OF POLICY OPTIONS IS APPROACHED FROM A SYSTEMS-THINKING PERSPECTIVE IN WHICH ALL OPTIONS ARE SEEN AS PART OF AN INTERRELATED AND SYNERGETIC COMPLEX.

Fostering inter-institutional collaboration

As an endeavour to provide globally an equal access to km-scale climate information, this effort requests international and inter-institutional collaboration. It could hence also open new opportunities for regions and stakeholder groups with scarce resources.

Embracing transdisciplinarity

Transdisciplinarity —collaborating across academic and non-academic expertise— is increasingly essential, as seen in the EU's research funding priorities. However, climate scientists already face enough challenges without needing to master complex social systems, communication, or societal engagement. Bringing in experts from diverse disciplines, skilled in service development and user interaction, would help bridge gaps between climate science and practical applications, ensuring that km-scale climate models produce services that are both useful and widely used.

Financing: multi-stakeholder partnerships

The private sector is expected to gain greatly with this science coming forth and they can be part of financing schemes that support such efforts, including public-private partnerships.

Reducing data access barriers

Direct data access demands high technical capacities on the side of users. Access to new data should not require sophisticated technology nor high performance computing. Indirectly diminishing the barriers to data access means working towards open private-public data protocols, standards and a new era of data sharing. Moreover, capacity building efforts should start from early-phases, allowing users to provide feedback to strengthen the services and gain ownership.

Retaining talent

Research institutions need to be aware of the demands placed upon early career researchers to advance km-scale models forward, and create incentives designed with the academic system in mind, which rewards publications, winning projects and advancing new lines of research. A balanced allocation of time between these activities and the needed technical activities, would be important to maintain.

About the Project

nextGEMS is a collaborative European project. Funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, it will tap expertise from fourteen European Nations to develop two next generation (storm-resolving) Earth-system Models. Through breakthroughs in simulation realism, these models will allow us to understand and reliably quantify how the climate will change on a global and regional scale, and how the weather, including its extreme events, will look like in the future.

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